

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of thiazolidinones derived from 4-methylcoumarinyl-7-oxyacetic hydrazide

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Abstract : A series of new thiazolidin-4-ones (**3a-j**), 5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones (**4a-l**) have been synthesised via the condensation of 4-methylcoumarinyl-7-oxyacetic acid [(substituted phenyl)methylene]hydrazides (**2a-l**), with thioglycolic acid and thiomalic acid respectively. The compounds (**2a-l**) were synthesised from 4-methylcoumarinyl-7-oxyacetic hydrazide using various aromatic aldehydes. The structure of all synthesised compounds has been determined by spectral methods. The compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* bacteria.

Keywords : Thiazolidin-4-ones, antibacterial activity, 4-methylcoumarinyl-7-oxyacetic hydrazide, thiomalic acid.

Introduction

Coumarin derivatives possess wide spectrum of biological activity which includes antioxidant activity¹, anti-inflammatory activity², antiangiogenesis activity³, platelet antiaggregatory activity⁴ and vasodilatory activity⁵. Also it is well documented that 4-thiazolidinones display pronounced antimicrobial activity⁶⁻⁹. In the light of above observations, it was considered of interest to synthesise 4-methylcoumarinyl-7-oxyacetic hydrazide incorporating thiazolidin-4-ones and 5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones and evaluate them for their antibacterial activity.

Results and discussion

The starting material 4-methylcoumarinyl-7-oxyacetic hydrazide **1** was prepared by the standard method available in the literature¹¹. The compound **1** on reaction with various aldehydes afforded Schiff bases (**2a-l**). The cycloaddition of thioglycolic acid and thiomalic acid to Schiff bases yielded the corresponding 4-thiazolidinones (**3a-j**) and 5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones (**4a-l**) respectively (Scheme 1).

Antibacterial activity¹⁰ :

Compounds **3a-j** and **4a-l** were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* at 250 mcg/disc concentration by filter paper disc technique. Standard antibacterial ciprofloxacin (5 mcg/disc) was also

Ar = 2-ClC₆H₄, 4-CH(CH₃)₂C₆H₄, 4-FC₆H₄, 4-CH₃C₆H₄, 3,4,5-(OCH₃)₃C₆H₂, 3-BrC₆H₄, 2,4-(Cl)₂C₆H₃, 3,4-(OCH₃)₂C₆H₃, 4-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄, C₆H₅, 3-OCH₃C₆H₄, 3-NO₂C₆H₄

Scheme 1

screened under similar conditions for comparison. It was observed that compound **3d** (*p*-methylphenyl derivative of thiazolidine-4-one) and **4a** (*o*-chlorophenyl derivative of 5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone) showed moderate

activity (zone of inhibition 18–19 mm) against *S. aureus*. The results of antibacterial screening showed **4a** to be moderately active (19 mm) and **3d** to be exhibiting highly significant activity (35 mm) against *B. subtilis*. Rest of the newly synthesised compounds was devoid of activity against both organisms.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and were uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr discs) were recorded on a JASCO FT/IR-410 spectrophotometer (Japan) and NMR spectra in DMSO-*d*₆ at 300 MHz on Brüker (Switzerland) instrument. Mass spectra were recorded on LC/MS (API-4000), MDS Sciex (Canada) and microanalytical data was obtained from Quest Research and Training Institute (India). The physical data of the compounds **3a-j** and **4a-l** are presented in Table 1.

4-Methylcoumarinyl-7-oxyacetic acid [(substituted phenyl)methylene]hydrazide^{12,13} (**2a-l**) :

A mixture of compound **1** (2.48 g, 0.01 mol), glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and substituted benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 8 h. The contents were then poured onto crushed ice. The resultant solid was filtered and recrystallised using glacial acetic acid.

*2-(Substituted phenyl)-3-(4'-methylcoumarinyl-7'-oxyacetamido)-4-thiazolidinone*¹² (**3a-j**) :

A homogenous mixture of compound **2a-j** (0.01 mol) and thioglycollic acid (0.92 g, 0.01 mol) in 20 ml of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 10 h. The reaction mixture was triturated with sodium bicarbonate solution (10%). The neutral solid resulted was poured onto crushed ice. The separated product was filtered off, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol. The ¹³C

Table 1. Characterisation data of the compounds **3a-j** and **4a-l**

Compd.	Ar	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	Elemental analysis (%) :		
					Found (Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
3a	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	202–204	56	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₅ S	56.46 (56.69)	3.76 (3.85)	6.49 (6.30)
3b	4-CH(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	180–183	58	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₅ S	63.93 (63.70)	5.29 (5.35)	6.01 (6.19)
3c	4-FC ₆ H ₄	228–230	72	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ FN ₂ O ₅ S	59.10 (58.87)	3.95 (4.00)	6.61 (6.54)
3d	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	154–155	64	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅ S	62.19 (62.25)	4.76 (4.75)	6.76 (6.60)
3e	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃ C ₆ H ₂	240–243	65	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₈ S	57.78 (57.59)	4.85 (4.83)	5.53 (5.60)
3f	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	234–236	70	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ BrN ₂ O ₅ S	51.35 (51.54)	3.63 (3.50)	5.67 (5.72)
3g	2,4-(Cl) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	281–282	68	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₅ S	52.68 (52.62)	3.31 (3.36)	5.73 (5.84)
3h	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	276–277	60	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₇ S	58.48 (58.71)	4.66 (4.71)	6.06 (5.95)
3i	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	148–150	62	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₅ S	60.94 (60.91)	5.03 (5.11)	9.43 (9.27)
3j	C ₆ H ₅	219–220	57	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅ S	61.51 (61.45)	4.33 (4.42)	6.78 (6.83)
4a	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	204–206	64	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₇ S	54.79 (54.93)	3.94 (3.81)	5.48 (5.57)
4b	4-CH(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	122–123	58	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₇ S	60.97 (61.16)	5.26 (5.13)	5.31 (5.49)
4c	4-FC ₆ H ₄	221–223	72	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ FN ₂ O ₇ S	56.39 (56.79)	4.02 (3.94)	5.67 (5.76)

				<i>Table-1 (contd.)</i>			
4d	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	196–197	64	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₇ S	59.51 (59.74)	4.55 (4.60)	5.65 (5.81)
4e	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃ C ₆ H ₂	136–138	62	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	55.97 (55.91)	4.64 (4.69)	5.09 (5.02)
4f	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	130–132	70	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ BrN ₂ O ₇ S	50.37 (50.47)	3.48 (3.50)	4.94 (5.12)
4g	2,4-(Cl) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	212–214	62	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₇ S	51.64 (51.41)	3.32 (3.38)	5.32 (5.21)
4h	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	230–231	76	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₉ S	56.86 (56.81)	4.45 (4.58)	5.19 (5.30)
4i	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	158–160	75	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₇ S	58.31 (58.70)	4.96 (4.93)	8.32 (8.21)
4j	C ₆ H ₅	178–179	60	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₇ S	59.02 (58.97)	4.34 (4.30)	5.93 (5.98)
4k	3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	156–158	65	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₈ S	57.87 (57.82)	4.43 (4.45)	5.57 (5.62)
4l	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	238–240	62	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₉ S	54.03 (53.80)	3.86 (3.73)	8.07 (8.18)

Table 2. ¹³C NMR data of compounds 3a and 3b

Compd.	¹³ C NMR (δ ppm)
3a	18.12 (CH ₃), 45.26 (C ₅), 52.63 (C ₂), 66.20 (-O-CH ₂ -), 101.62 (C ₈), 112.39 (C ₃), 113.67–126.49 (aromatic carbons, C ₅ , C ₆ , C ₇ , C ₉ and C ₁₀), 153.36 (C ₄), 160.55 (C ₂), 154.46 (-NH-C=O), 166.14 (C ₄)
3b	18.12 (CH ₃), 23.63 (isopropyl (CH ₃) ₂), 38.57 (isopropyl CH), 48.23 (C ₅), 57.06 (C ₂), 63.53 (-O-CH ₂ -), 101.61 (C ₈), 111.46 (C ₃), 113.53–126.72 (aromatic carbons, C ₅ , C ₆ , C ₇ , C ₉ and C ₁₀), 154.45 (C ₄), 161.18 (C ₂), 165.89 (-NH-C=O), 170.59 (C ₄)

Table 3. ¹H NMR data of compounds 3a-j and 4a-l

Compd.	¹ H NMR (δ ppm)
3a	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 3.36 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.84 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.33 (1H, s, H-2), 6.25 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.99–7.55 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.73 (1H, s, NH)
3b	1.18–1.22 (6H, d, isopropyl CH ₃), 2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.52 (2H, s, CH ₂), 2.8–3.0 (1H, m, isopropyl CH), 4.8 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.29 (1H, s, H-2), 6.25 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.97–7.99 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.32 (1H, s, NH)
3c	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.50 (2H, s, CH ₂), 5.25 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.25 (1H, s, H-2), 6.87 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.71–8.32 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.31 (1H, s, NH)
3d	2.34 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 3.35 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.80 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.28 (1H, s, H-2), 6.24 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.97–7.75 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.28 (1H, s, NH)

Table-3 (contd.)

3e	2.40 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 3.32 (2H, s, CH ₂), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH ₃ at C ₄ ' of phenyl group), 3.82 (6H, s, OCH ₃ at C ₃ ' and C ₅ ' of phenyl group), 4.77 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.32 (1H, s, H-2), 6.21 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.00–7.73 (6H, m, Ar-H), 10.3 (1H, s, NH)
3f	2.40 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 3.41 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.78 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.12 (1H, s, H-2), 6.25 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.95–7.06 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.74 (1H, s, NH)
3g	2.40 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 3.42 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.78 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.32 (1H, s, H-2), 6.23 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.90–8.30 (6H, m, Ar-H), 10.3 (1H, s, NH)
3h	2.40 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.50 (2H, s, CH ₂), 3.74–3.80 (6H, m, OCH ₃), 4.78 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.30 (1H, s, H-2), 6.23 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.84–8.25 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.38 (1H, s, NH)
3i	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.97 (6H, s, N(CH ₃) ₂), 3.34 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.78 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.24 (1H, s, H-2), 6.71 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.91–7.73 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.5 (1H, s, NH)
3j	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 3.41 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.78 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.31 (1H, s, H-2), 6.25 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.99–7.74 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.02 (1H, s, NH)
4a	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.50–2.73 (2H, d, CH ₂), 4.78 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.33 (1H, s, H-2), 6.23 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.0–7.73 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.98–8.10 (1H, t, H-5), 8.41 (1H, s, NH), 10.31 (1H, s, COOH)
4b	1.15–1.24 (6H, d, isopropyl CH ₃), 2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.50–2.51 (2H, d, CH ₂), 2.9–3.0 (1H, m, isopropyl CH), 4.8 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.30 (1H, s, H-2), 6.20 (1H, s, H-3')

Table-3 (contd.)

	6.9–7.8 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.90–8.00 (1H, t, H-5), 8.30 (1H, s, NH), 10.30 (1H, s, COOH)
4c	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.50–2.62 (2H, d, CH ₂), 4.78 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.31 (1H, s, H-2), 6.25 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.98–7.80 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.02 (1H, t, H-5), 8.33 (1H, s, NH), 11.69 (1H, s, COOH)
4d	2.33 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 2.40 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.49–2.51 (2H, d, CH ₂), 4.80 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.30 (1H, s, H-2), 6.24 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.9–7.8 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.75–7.98 (1H, t, H-5), 8.30 (1H, s, NH), 10.30 (1H, s, COOH)
4e	2.40 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.49–2.51 (2H, d, CH ₂), 3.70 (3H, s, OCH ₃ at C ₄ ' of phenyl group), 3.82 (6H, s, OCH ₃ at C ₃ ' and C ₅ ' of phenyl group), 4.74 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.33 (1H, s, H-2), 6.24 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.85–7.75 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.93 (1H, t, H-5), 8.24 (1H, s, NH), 10.32 (1H, s, COOH)
4f	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.49–2.51 (2H, d, CH ₂), 4.74 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.87 (1H, s, H-2), 6.20 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.85–7.06 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.65–7.74 (2H, m, NH and H-5), 10.32 (1H, s, COOH)
4g	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.50–2.72 (2H, d, CH ₂), 4.84 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.33 (1H, s, H-2), 6.24 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.99–7.53 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.95–7.98 (1H, t, H-5), 8.35 (1H, s, NH), 10.15 (1H, s, COOH)
4h	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.50–2.57 (2H, d, CH ₂), 3.37–3.43 (6H, m, OCH ₃), 4.74 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.32 (1H, s, H-2), 6.23 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.95–7.06 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.68–7.74 (2H, m, NH and H-5), 10.32 (1H, s, COOH)
4i	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.49–2.51 (2H, d, CH ₂), 3.37 (6H, s, N(CH ₃) ₂), 4.78–4.88 (3H, m, OCH ₂ and H-2), 6.25 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.96–7.06 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.63–7.74 (2H, m, H-5 and NH), 10.32 (1H, s, COOH)
4j	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.50–2.51 (2H, d, CH ₂), 4.70 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.31 (1H, s, H-2), 6.24 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.97–8.02 (10H, m, Ar-H, H-5 and NH), 10.32 (1H, s, COOH)
4k	2.48 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.57–2.58 (2H, d, CH ₂), 3.87 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.89 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.40 (1H, s, H-2), 6.31 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.04–7.83 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.83–8.06 (1H, t, H-5), 8.40 (1H, s, NH), 10.39 (1H, s, COOH)
4l	2.41 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.49–2.51 (2H, d, CH ₂), 4.86 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.37 (1H, s, H-2), 6.25 (1H, s, H-3'), 6.96–7.10 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.68–7.77 (1H, t, H-5), 8.41 (1H, s, NH), 10.31 (1H, s, COOH)

NMR spectral data of compounds **3a** and **3b** are given in Table 2 and ¹H NMR spectral data of compounds **3a-j** are given in Table 3; **3a** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3341 (NH), 2809 (CH₂), 1721 (C=O), 1259 (coumarinyl C–O–C-), 1076

(Ar-Cl); MS (*m/z*) : 445 (M⁺), 447 (M+2)⁺, 411, 371, 291, 149; **3b** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3260 (NH), 2959 (CH₂), 1698 (C=O), 1202 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); MS (*m/z*) : 453 (M⁺), 379, 291, 249, 149; **3c** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3283 (NH), 2852 (CH₂), 1709 (C=O), 1273 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); MS (*m/z*) : 429 (M+1)⁺, 355, 291, 249, 177; **3d** IR (cm⁻¹) : 2981 (methyl CH), 2807 (CH₂), 1716 (C=O), 1273 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); MS (*m/z*) : 425 (M+1)⁺, 291, 249, 177, 149; **3e** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3306 (NH), 2851 (CH₂), 1733 (C=O), 1273 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); **3f** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3092 (aromatic CH), 2807 (CH₂), 1726 (C=O), 1267 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); **3g** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3292 (NH), 2807 (CH₂), 1723 (C=O), 1269 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); **3h** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3092 (aromatic CH), 2830 (CH₂), 1728 (C=O), 1268 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); **3i** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3296 (NH), 2811 (CH₂), 1726 (C=O), 1273 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); **3j** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3178 (NH), 2972 (CH₂), 1713 (C=O), 1269 (coumarinyl C–O–C-).

2-(Substituted phenyl)-3-(4'-methylcoumarinyl-7'-oxyacetamido)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone¹² (**4a-l**) :

A homogenous mixture of compound **2a-l** (0.01 mol) and thiomalic acid (1.52 g, 0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. The reaction mixture was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated by hydrochloric acid (10%) and recrystallised from ethanol. The ¹H NMR spectral data of compounds **4a-l** are given in Table 3. **4a** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3265 (OH), 1713 (C=O), 1512 (ring C=C), 1273 (coumarinyl C–O–C-), 1080 (C-Cl); MS (*m/z*) : 503.3 (M⁺), 505.3 (M+2)⁺, 371, 291, 149; **4b** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3306 (OH), 1731 (C=O), 1595 (ring C=C), 1273 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); MS (*m/z*) : 511 (M⁺), 493, 465, 379, 149; **4c** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3408 (OH), 1711 (C=O), 1507 (ring C=C), 1229 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); MS (*m/z*) : 487 (M+1)⁺, 355, 291, 249, 149; **4d** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3308 (OH), 1713 (C=O), 1508 (ring C=C), 1202 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); MS (*m/z*) : (M⁺) 483, 351, 291, 249, 149; **4e** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3482 (OH), 1735 (C=O), 1580 (ring C=C), 1272 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); **4f** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3486 (OH), 1733 (C=O), 1540 (ring C=C), 1274 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); **4g** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3449 (OH), 1698 (C=O), 1586 (ring C=C), 1268 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); **4h** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3490 (OH), 1509 (ring C=C), 1736 (C=O), 1273 (coumarinyl C–O–C-); **4i** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3486 (OH), 1735 (C=O), 1455

(ring C=C), 1275 (coumarinyl C-O-C-); **4j** IR (cm^{-1}) : 3481 (OH), 3088 (aromatic CH), 1737 (C=O), 1271 (coumarinyl C-O-C-); **4k** IR (cm^{-1}) : 3444 (OH), 3087 (aromatic CH), 1735 (C=O), 1273 (coumarinyl C-O-C-); **4l** IR (cm^{-1}) : 3425 (OH), 1734 (C=O), 1423 (ring C=C), 1252 (coumarinyl C-O-C-).

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